
**ON A SEQUENCE OF POLYNOMIALS WITH HYPOTHETICALLY
INTEGER COEFFICIENTS**

Vladimir Shevelev

Dept. of Mathematics, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beersheva, Israel
shevelev@bgu.ac.il

Peter J. C. Moses

Moparmatic Company, Astwood Bank, Nr. Redditch, Worcestershire, England
mows@mopar.freereserve.co.uk

Received: 3/31/12, Revised: 12/11/12, Accepted: 2/3/13, Published: 2/8/13

Abstract

The first author introduced a sequence of polynomials defined recursively. One of the main results of this study is proof of the integrality of its coefficients.

1. Introduction

In point of fact, there are only a few examples of sequences known where the question of the integrality of the terms is a difficult problem. In 1989, Somos [9] posed a problem on the integrality of sequences depending on parameter $k \geq 4$ which are defined by the recursion

$$a_n = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor} a_{n-j} a_{n-(k-j)}}{a_{n-k}}, \quad n \geq k \geq 4,$$

with the initial conditions $a_i = 1$, $i = 1, \dots, k-1$.

Gale [3] proved the integrality of Somos sequences when $k = 4$ and 5, attributing a proof to Malouf [4]. Hickerson and Stanley (see [6]) independently proved the integrality of the $k = 6$ case in unpublished work and Fomin and Zelevinsky (2002) gave the first published proof. Finally, Lotto (1990) gave an unpublished proof for the $k = 7$ case. These are sequences A006720-A006723 in [8]. It is interesting that, for $k \geq 8$, the property of integrality disappears (see sequence A030127 in [8]). In connection with this, note that in the so-called Göbel's sequence ([11]) defined by the recursion

$$x_n = \frac{1}{n} \left(1 + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i^2 \right), \quad n \geq 1, \quad x_0 = 1,$$

the first non-integer term is $x_{43} = 5.4093 \times 10^{178485291567}$.

In this paper we study the Shevelev sequence of polynomials $\{P_n(x)\}_{n \geq 1}$ that are defined by the following recursion: $P_1 = 1$, $P_2 = 1$, and, for $n \geq 2$,

$$4(2x + n)P_{n+1}(x) = 2(x + n)P_n(x) + (2x + n)P_n(x + 1) + (4x + n)l_n(x), \text{ if } n \text{ is odd,} \tag{1}$$

$$4P_{n+1}(x) = 4(x + n)P_n(x) + 2(2x + n + 1)P_n(x + 1) + (4x + n)l_{n-1}(x), \text{ if } n \text{ is even,} \tag{2}$$

where

$$l_n(x) = (x + \frac{n-1}{2})(x + \frac{n-3}{2}) \cdots (x + 1).$$

The first few polynomials are ([8], sequence A174531):

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= 1, \\ P_2 &= 1, \\ P_3 &= 3x + 4, \\ P_4 &= 2x + 4, \\ P_5 &= 5x^2 + 25x + 32, \\ P_6 &= 3x^2 + 19x + 32, \\ P_7 &= 7x^3 + 77x^2 + 294x + 384, \\ P_8 &= 4x^3 + 52x^2 + 240x + 384, \\ P_9 &= 9x^4 + 174x^3 + 1323x^2 + 4614x + 6144, \\ P_{10} &= 5x^4 + 110x^3 + 967x^2 + 3934x + 6144, \\ P_{11} &= 11x^5 + 330x^4 + 4169x^3 + 27258x^2 + 90992x + 122880, \\ P_{12} &= 6x^5 + 200x^4 + 2842x^3 + 21040x^2 + 79832x + 122880. \end{aligned}$$

According to our observations, the following conjectures are natural.

- 1) The coefficients of all the polynomials are integers. Moreover, the greatest common divisor of all coefficients is $n/rad(n)$, where $rad(n) = \prod_{p|n} p$;
- 2) $P_n(0) = 4^{\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor} \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor!$;
- 3) For even n , $P_n(1) = (2^n - 1)(\frac{n}{2})!/(n + 1)$, and for odd n , $P_n(1) = (2^n - 1)(\frac{n-1}{2})!$;
- 4) $P_n(x)$ has a real rational root if and only if either $n = 3$ or $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. In the latter case, such a unique root is $-\frac{n}{2}$;

- 5) Coefficients of x^k increase when k decreases;
- 6) If n is even, then the coefficients of P_n do not exceed the corresponding coefficients of P_{n-1} and the equality holds only for the last ones; moreover, the ratios of coefficients of x^k of polynomials P_{n-1} and P_n monotonically decrease to 1 when k decreases;
- 7) All coefficients of P_n , except of the last one, are multiples of n if and only if n is prime.

The main results of our paper consist of the following two theorems.

Theorem 1. (Explicit formula for $P_n(k)$) *For an integer k we have*

$$P_n(k) = \begin{cases} \left(\binom{(n-1)/2+k-1}{k-1} / \binom{n+2k-2}{k-1} \right) \left(\frac{n-1}{2} \right)! T_n(k), & \text{if } n \geq 1 \text{ is odd} \\ \left(\binom{n/2+k-1}{k} / \binom{n+2k-1}{k} \right) \left(\frac{n}{2} - 1 \right)! T_n(k), & \text{if } n \geq 2 \text{ is even,} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

$$= 2^{-\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + k - 1} \frac{(n+k-1)!}{(2\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 2k-1)!!} T_n(k), \tag{4}$$

where

$$T_n(k) = \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{i-1} \binom{n+2k-i-1}{k-1}. \tag{5}$$

Using Theorem 1, we prove Conjectures (2), (3) and the following main result.

Theorem 2. *For $n \geq 1$, $P_n(x)$ is a polynomial of degree $\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$ with integer coefficients.*

Nevertheless, the subtle second part of Conjecture (1) remains open.

2. Representation of $P_n(k)$ Via a Polynomial in n of Degree $k - 1$ with Integer Coefficients

Theorem 3. *For integers $k \geq 1$, $n \geq 1$, the following recursion holds*

$$P_n(k) = c_n(k) \left(2^{n+k-1} - \frac{R_k(n)}{(2k-2)!!} \right), \tag{6}$$

where $R_k(n)$ is a polynomial in n of degree $k - 1$ with integer coefficients and

$$c_n(k) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{n-1}{2} \right)! \prod_{i=1}^{k-1} \frac{n+i}{n+2i}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{n}{2} - 1 \right)! \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} \frac{n+i}{n+2i+1}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Proof. Write (3) and (4) in the form

$$P_n(k+1) = -\frac{2f}{g}P_n(k) + 4P_{n+1}(k) - \frac{h}{g}\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \binom{\frac{g-1}{2}}{k}, \text{ if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}; \quad (8)$$

$$P_n(k+1) = -\frac{2f}{g+1}P_n(k) + \frac{2}{g+1}P_{n+1}(k) - \frac{h}{2(g+1)}\left(\frac{n}{2}-1\right)! \binom{\frac{g}{2}-1}{k} \quad (9)$$

if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$,

where $f = n + k$, $g = n + 2k$, $h = n + 4k$.

Let n be odd. We use induction over k . For $k = 1$, (6) gives

$$R_1(n) = 2^n - \frac{P_n(1)}{c_n(1)} = \text{Const}(k). \quad (10)$$

Thus the base of induction is valid. Suppose the theorem is true for some value of k . Then, using this supposition and (6) to (9), we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_n(k+1) = & \\ & -\frac{2f}{g}\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \left(2^{n+k-1} - \frac{R_k(n)}{(2k-2)!!}\right) \prod_{i=1}^{k-1} \frac{n+i}{n+2i} + \\ & 2\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \left(2^{n+k} - \frac{R_k(n+1)}{(2k-2)!!}\right) \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} \frac{n+i+1}{n+2i+2} - \\ & \frac{h}{g}\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \frac{\frac{g-1}{2} \frac{g-3}{2} \dots \frac{n+1}{2}}{k!}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$\frac{f}{g} \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} \frac{n+i}{n+2i} = \prod_{j=1}^k \frac{n+j}{n+2j} = \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} \frac{n+i+1}{n+2i+2}.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} P_n(k+1) = & \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \left(-2^{n+k} + \frac{2R_k(n)}{(2k-2)!!} + 2^{n+k+1} - \right. \\ & \left. \frac{2R_k(n+1)}{(2k-2)!!} - \frac{h}{g} \frac{\frac{g-1}{2} \frac{g-3}{2} \dots \frac{n+1}{2}}{k!} \prod_{j=1}^k \frac{n+2j}{n+j}\right) \prod_{j=1}^k \frac{n+j}{n+2j}. \end{aligned}$$

Here we note that

$$(g-1)(g-3)\dots(n+1) \prod_{j=1}^k \frac{n+2j}{n+j} = (n+2k)_k,$$

where $(x)_k$ is a falling factorial. Hence

$$P_n(k+1) = c_n(k+1) \left(2^{n+k} - 2 \frac{R_k(n+1) - R_k(n)}{(2k-2)!!} - \frac{4k+n}{(2k)!!} (n+2k-1)_{k-1} \right) = c_n(k+1) \left(2^{n+k} - \frac{R_{k+1}(n)}{(2k)!!} \right),$$

where

$$R_{k+1}(n) = 4k(R_k(n+1) - R_k(n)) + (4k+n)(n+2k-1)_{k-1}. \tag{11}$$

Since, by the inductive supposition, $R_k(n)$ is a polynomial of degree $k-1$ with integer coefficients, then, by (11), $R_{k+1}(n)$ is a polynomial of degree k with integer coefficients. Note that the case of even n is considered quite analogously, obtaining the *same* formula (11). $\square$

In (6) and (7), put $n = 1$. Then, for $k \geq 1$ we have

$$\left(2^k - \frac{R_k(1)}{(2k-2)!!} \right) \frac{k!}{(2k-1)!!} = 1,$$

from which

$$R_k(1) = (k-1)! \left(2^{2k-1} - \binom{2k-1}{k} \right). \tag{12}$$

In particular, $R_1(1) = 1$ and, since $R_1(n)$ is of degree 0, $R_1(n) = 1$. Further, we find polynomials $R_k(n)$ using the recursion (11). The first polynomials $R_k(n)$ are

$$\begin{aligned} R_1(n) &= 1, \\ R_2(n) &= n + 4, \\ R_3(n) &= n^2 + 11n + 32, \\ R_4(n) &= n^3 + 21n^2 + 152n + 384, \\ R_5(n) &= n^4 + 34n^3 + 443n^2 + 2642n + 6144, \\ R_6(n) &= n^5 + 50n^4 + 1015n^3 + 10510n^2 + 55864n + 122880. \end{aligned}$$

3. Proof of Conjectures (2) and (3)

We start with the proof of Conjecture (3) for $P_n(1)$.

Proof. Note that, since $R_1(n) = 1$, from (10) we find

$$P_n(1) = c_n(1)(2^n - 1). \tag{13}$$

Besides, by (7), we have

$$c_n(1) = \begin{cases} (\frac{n-1}{2})!, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ \frac{1}{2}(\frac{n}{2} - 1)! \frac{n}{n+1} = (\frac{n}{2})!/(n+1), & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \end{cases} \tag{14}$$

and Conjecture (3) follows. □

Let us now prove Conjecture (2).

Proof. Note that (8) and (9), as in (1) and (2), are valid for every nonnegative k . For $k = 0$ and odd $n \geq 1$, (8) gives

$$P_n(1) = -2P_n(0) + 4P_{n+1}(0) - (\frac{n-1}{2})!,$$

or, using (13) and (14), we have

$$4P_{n+1}(0) - 2P_n(0) = 2^n (\frac{n-1}{2})!$$

Analogously, for $k = 0$ and even $n \geq 1$, from (9), (13) and (14) we find

$$P_{n+1}(0) - nP_n(0) = 2^{n-1} (\frac{n}{2})!$$

Thus

$$P_{n+1}(0) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}P_n(0) + 2^{n-2}(\frac{n-1}{2})!, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ nP_n(0) + 2^{n-1}(\frac{n}{2})!, & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

with $P_1(0) = 1$, $P_2(0) = 1$. Since the difference equation

$$y(n+1) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}y(n) + 2^{n-2}(\frac{n-1}{2})!, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ ny(n) + 2^{n-1}(\frac{n}{2})!, & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

with the initial values $y(1) = 1$, $y(2) = 1$ has an unique solution, it is sufficient to verify that $y(n) = P_n(0) = 4^{\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor} \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor!$ is a solution. □

4. Explicit Formula for $R_k(n)$

Since from (11)

$$4kR_k(n + 1) = 4kR_k(n) + R_{k+1}(n) - (4k + n)(n + 2k - 1)_{k-1}, \tag{15}$$

we have a recursion in n for $R_k(n)$ given by (12) and (15).

Our aim in this section is to find a generalization of (12) for an arbitrary integer $n \geq 1$. Note that we can write (12) in the form

$$R_k(1) = 2(k - 1)!4^{k-1} - \frac{(2k - 1)!}{k!}.$$

Using (15) and (12), after some transformations, we find

$$R_k(2) = 2^2(k - 1)!4^{k-1} - 2\frac{(2k - 1)!}{k!} - \frac{(2k)!}{(k + 1)!}.$$

The regularity is fixed in the following theorem.

Theorem 4. *For integer $k \geq 1$, $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$R_k(n) = 2^n(k - 1)!4^{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{n-i} \frac{(2k + i - 2)!}{(k + i - 1)!}. \tag{16}$$

Proof. Taking into account that $\frac{(2k+i-2)!}{(k+i-1)!} = \binom{2k+i-2}{k-1}(k-1)!$, we prove (16) in the following equivalent form:

$$R_k(n) = 2^n(k - 1)! \left(4^{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k + i - 2}{k - 1} \right). \tag{17}$$

We use induction over n . Suppose that (17) is valid for some value of n and an arbitrary integer $k \geq 1$. By (15), we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_k(n + 1) &= 2^n(k - 1)! \left(4^{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k + i - 2}{k - 1} \right) + \\ &2^{n-2}(k - 1)! \left(4^k - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k + i}{k} \right) - \frac{4k + n}{4k} (n + 2k - 1)_{k-1} = \\ &2^n(k - 1)! \left(4^{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k + i - 2}{k - 1} \right) + 2^n(k - 1)! \left(4^{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i-2} \binom{2k + i}{k} \right) - \\ &\frac{(n + 2k - 1)!}{(n + k)!} - \frac{n}{4k} \frac{(n + 2k - 1)!}{(n + k)!}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus we should prove the identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2^{n+1}(k-1)!4^{k-1} - 2^n(k-1)! \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k+i-2}{k-1} - \\
 & 2^{n-2}(k-1)! \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k+i}{k} - \frac{n+4k}{4k} \frac{(n+2k-1)!}{(n+k)!} = \\
 & 2^{n+1}(k-1)! \left(4^{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} 2^{-i} \binom{2k+i-2}{k-1} \right),
 \end{aligned}$$

which is easily reduced to the identity

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4 \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k+i-2}{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k+i}{k} = \\
 & 2^{-n} \frac{n+4k}{4k} \frac{(n+2k-1)!}{(n+k)!} - 4 \cdot 2^{-n} \binom{2k+n-1}{k-1}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that, the right hand part is $\frac{n}{k2^n} \binom{2k+n-1}{k-1}$. Therefore, it is left to prove the identity

$$4 \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k+i-2}{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{-i} \binom{2k+i}{k} = \frac{n}{2^n k} \binom{2k+n-1}{k-1}.$$

Since this is trivially satisfied for $n = 0$, it is sufficient to verify the equality of the first differences of the left and the right hand parts, which is reduced to the identity

$$2(n+2k-1) \binom{2k+n-2}{k-1} = n \binom{2k+n-1}{k-1} + k \binom{2k+n}{k},$$

which is verified directly. □

5. Proof of Theorem 1

Now we are able to prove Theorem 1.

Proof. According to (5), we have

$$T_n(k) = \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{i-1} \binom{n+2k-i-1}{k-1} = \sum_{j=1}^n 2^{n-j} \binom{2k+j-2}{k-1}. \tag{18}$$

Hence, by (17), we find

$$R_k(n) = 2^n(k-1)! (4^{k-1} - 2^{-n} T_n(k)) =$$

$$(k - 1)!(2^{n+2k-2} - T_n(k)). \tag{19}$$

Now from (6) and (19) we have

$$P_n(k) = 2^{-(k-1)}c_n(k)T_n(k). \tag{20}$$

Let n be odd. Note that, by (7),

$$\begin{aligned} 2^{-(k-1)}c_n(k) &= \\ 2^{-(k-1)}\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \frac{(n+k-1)(n+k-2)\cdots(n+1)}{(n+2k-2)(n+2k-4)\cdots(n+2)} &= \\ 2^{-(k-1)}\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \frac{(n+k-1)n!!}{n!(n+2k-2)!!} &. \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Taking into account that

$$n!! = \frac{n!}{(n-1)!!} = \frac{n!}{2^{\frac{n-1}{2}}\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)!}, \tag{22}$$

we find from (21)

$$\begin{aligned} 2^{-(k-1)}c_n(k) &= \frac{(n+k-1)!\left(\frac{n-1}{2}+k-1\right)!}{(n+2k-2)!} = \\ \frac{\left(\frac{n-1}{2}+k-1\right)!}{(k-1)!\binom{n+2k-2}{k-1}} &= \frac{\binom{\frac{n-1}{2}+k-1}{k-1}}{\binom{n+2k-2}{k-1}} \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \end{aligned}$$

and (3) follows from (20). Furthermore, since by (22) $\frac{n!!\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)!}{n!} = 2^{-\frac{n-1}{2}}$, from (20) and (21) we find

$$P_n(k) = 2^{-\left(\frac{n-1}{2}+k-1\right)} \frac{(n+k-1)!}{(n+2k-2)!!} T_n(k)$$

corresponds to (4) in the case of odd n . The case of even n is considered quite analogously. □

6. Bisection of Sequence $\{P_n(x)\}$

Note that $T_n(k)$, (5), has rather a simple structure, which allows us to find different relations for it. Using (3) and (4), we are able to find recursion relations for $P_n(x)$ which are simpler than the basis recursion (1) and (2). We start with the following simple recursions for $T_n(k)$.

Lemma 5.

$$T_n(k) - 2T_{n-1}(k) = \binom{n+2k-2}{k-1}, \quad k \geq 1; \tag{23}$$

$$T_n(k) - 4T_{n-2}(k) = \binom{n+2k-2}{k-1} + 2\binom{n+2k-3}{k-1}, \quad k \geq 2. \tag{24}$$

Proof. By (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_n(k) - 2T_{n-1}(k) &= \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{i-1} \binom{n+2k-i-1}{k-1} - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} 2^j \binom{n+2k-j-2}{k-1} = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{i-1} \binom{n+2k-i-1}{k-1} - \sum_{i=2}^n 2^{i-1} \binom{n+2k-i-1}{k-1} \end{aligned}$$

and (23) follows; (24) is a simple corollary of (23). □

Theorem 6. (Bisection) *If $n \geq 3$ is odd, then*

$$\begin{aligned} (2x+n-2)P_n(x) &= 2(x+n-1)(x+n-2)P_{n-2}(x)+ \\ &= (4x+3n-4)\left(x+\frac{n-1}{2}-1\right)\left(x+\frac{n-1}{2}-2\right)\cdots x; \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

if $n \geq 4$ is even, then

$$\begin{aligned} (2x+n-1)P_n(x) &= 2(x+n-1)(x+n-2)P_{n-2}(x)+ \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(4x+3n-4)\left(x+\frac{n-2}{2}-1\right)\left(x+\frac{n-2}{2}-2\right)\cdots x. \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Proof. According to (3), we have

$$T_n(k) = \begin{cases} \binom{n+2k-2}{k-1} / \left(\binom{(n-1)/2+k-1}{k-1} \left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)! \right) P_n(k), & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ \binom{n+2k-1}{k} / \left(\binom{n/2+k-1}{k} \left(\frac{n}{2}-1\right)! \right) P_n(k), & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \tag{27}$$

Substituting this to (24), after simple transformations, we obtain (25) and (26), where k is replaced by arbitrary x . □

Note that from (25) and (26), using a simple induction, we conclude that, for even $n \geq 4$, $P_n(x)$ is a polynomial of degree $\frac{n-2}{2}$, while, for odd $n \geq 3$, $P_n(x)$ is a polynomial of degree $\frac{n-1}{2}$. However, the structure of formulas (25) and (26) does not allow us to prove that all coefficients of $P_n(x)$ are integer. This will be done in the following section by the discovery of the special relationships with the required structure.

7. Proof of Theorem 2

Lemma 7. For $n \geq 1$, we have

$$T_n(k) - T_{n-2}(k+1) = \binom{n+2k-1}{k}. \tag{28}$$

Proof. By (18), we should prove that

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{2k+n-1}{k} &= T_n(k) - T_{n-2}(k+1) = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n 2^{n-j} \binom{2k+j-2}{k-1} - \sum_{j=1}^{n-2} 2^{n-j-2} \binom{2k+j}{k} = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n 2^{n-j} \binom{2k+j-2}{k-1} - \sum_{i=1}^n 2^{n-i} \binom{2k+i-2}{k} + \\ &= 2^{n-1} \binom{2k-1}{k} + 2^{n-2} \binom{2k}{k}, \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{j=1}^n 2^{-j} \left(\binom{2k+j-2}{k-1} - \binom{2k+j-2}{k} \right) = \\ &= 2^{-n} \binom{2k+n-1}{k} - \frac{1}{2} \binom{2k-1}{k} - \frac{1}{4} \binom{2k}{k}. \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

It is verified directly that (29) is valid for $n = 1$. Therefore, it is sufficient to verify that the first differences over n of the left hand side and the right hand side coincide. The corresponding identity

$$\begin{aligned} &2^{-n} \left(\binom{2k+n-2}{k-1} - \binom{2k+n-2}{k} \right) = \\ &= 2^{-n} \binom{2k+n-1}{k} - 2^{-n+1} \binom{2k+n-2}{k} \end{aligned}$$

reduces to the equality $\binom{2k+n-2}{k-1} + \binom{2k+n-2}{k} = \binom{2k+n-1}{k}$.

Now we are able to complete proof of Theorem 2. Considering even $n \geq 4$, by (27), we obtain the following relation for $P_n(k)$ corresponding to (28):

$$\begin{aligned} P_n(x) &= (n+x-1)P_{n-2}(x+1) + \\ &= \left(x + \frac{n}{2} - 1\right) \left(x + \frac{n}{2} - 2\right) \cdots (x+1). \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

On the other hand, using (23), for odd $n \geq 3$, we obtain the following relation

$$P_n(x) = 2(x + n - 1)P_{n-1}(x) + \left(x + \frac{n-1}{2} - 1\right)\left(x + \frac{n-1}{2} - 2\right) \cdots x. \tag{31}$$

From (30), by simple induction, we see that, for even $n \geq 4$, $P_n(x)$ is a polynomial with integer coefficients. Then from (31) we find that $P_n(x)$, for odd n , is also a polynomial with integer coefficients. $\square$

8. Other Relations

Together with (25), (26), (30) and (31) there exist many other relations for $P_n(x)$. All of them are corollaries of the corresponding relations for $T_n(k)$. Below we give a few pairs of some such relations.

As we saw, for odd $n \geq 3$, (31) follows from (23). Let us consider even $n \geq 4$. Then we obtain the second component of the following recursion

$$P_n(x) = \begin{cases} 2(x + n - 1)P_{n-1}(x) + \\ ((x + n - 1)P_{n-1}(x) + \\ \left(x + \frac{n-1}{2} - 1\right)\left(x + \frac{n-1}{2} - 2\right) \cdots x, \text{ if } n \geq 3 \text{ is odd,} \\ \left(x + \frac{n}{2} - 1\right)\left(x + \frac{n}{2} - 2\right) \cdots x / (2x + n - 1), \text{ if } n \geq 4 \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

Lemma 8. For $n \geq 1$, $k \geq 1$, we have

$$T_n(k + 1) = 4T_n(k) - \frac{n}{k} \binom{n + 2k - 1}{k - 1}. \tag{32}$$

Proof. By (24) and (28), we have

$$T_n(k + 1) = T_{n+2}(k) - \binom{n + 2k + 1}{k} = 4T_n(k) + \binom{n + 2k}{k - 1} + 2 \binom{n + 2k - 1}{k - 1} - \binom{n + 2k + 1}{k}.$$

It is left to note that

$$\binom{n + 2k}{k - 1} + 2 \binom{n + 2k - 1}{k - 1} - \binom{n + 2k + 1}{k} = -\frac{n}{k} \binom{n + 2k - 1}{k - 1}.$$

$\square$

From Lemma 8 and (27) we find the following recursion

$$\begin{cases} (2x+n)P_n(x+1) = 2(x+n)P_n(x) - \\ (2x+n+1)P_n(x+1) = 2(x+n)P_n(x) - \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} n(x + \frac{n-1}{2})(x + \frac{n-1}{2} - 1) \cdots (x+1), \text{ if } n \geq 3 \text{ is odd,} \\ \frac{n}{2}(x + \frac{n}{2} - 1)(x + \frac{n}{2} - 2) \cdots (x+1), \text{ if } n \geq 4 \text{ is even.} \end{array} \right. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 9. For $n \geq 2$, $k \geq 1$, we have

$$(n+k-1)(T_n(k) - 4T_n(k-1)) = n(T_{n-1}(k) - 2T_n(k-1)). \tag{33}$$

Proof. By (32),

$$T_n(k) - 4T_n(k-1) = -\frac{n}{k-1} \binom{n+2k-3}{k-2}. \tag{34}$$

By (23),

$$T_n(k-1) = 2T_{n-1}(k-1) + \binom{n+2k-4}{k-2}.$$

Therefore,

$$T_{n-1}(k) - 2T_n(k-1) = T_{n-1}(k) - 4T_{n-1}(k-1) - 2 \binom{n+2k-4}{k-2}.$$

Using again (32), we find

$$T_{n-1}(k) - 2T_n(k-1) = -\left(\frac{n-1}{k-1} + 2\right) \binom{n+2k-4}{k-2}. \tag{35}$$

Now the lemma follows from (34) and (35) since $(n+k-1) \binom{n+2k-3}{k-2} = (n+2k-3) \binom{n+2k-4}{k-2}$. □

Going from (33) to the corresponding formula for $P_n(x)$ in the case of odd $n \geq 3$ unexpectedly leads to a very simple homogeneous relation

$$P_n(x) = P_n(x-1) + nP_{n-1}(x) \tag{36}$$

which we use in Sections 9 and 12. The corresponding relation for even $n \geq 4$ is

$$(2x+n-1)P_n(x) = (2x+n-2)P_n(x-1) + \frac{n}{2}P_{n-1}(x). \tag{37}$$

Lemma 10. For $n \geq 1$, $k \geq 2$, we have

$$2T_n(k) - T_{n-1}(k+1) = \binom{n+2k-1}{k}.$$

Proof. By (23), we have

$$2T_n(k) - T_{n-1}(k+1) = 4T_{n-1}(k) + 2\binom{n+2k-2}{k-1} - T_{n-1}(k+1).$$

Furthermore, by (28),

$$T_{n-1}(k+1) = T_{n+1}(k) - \binom{n+2k}{k}.$$

Hence,

$$2T_n(k) - T_{n-1}(k+1) = 4T_{n-1}(k) - T_{n+1}(k) + 2\binom{n+2k-2}{k-1} + \binom{n+2k}{k}. \tag{38}$$

Finally, by (24),

$$T_{n+1}(k) - 4T_{n-1}(k) = \binom{n+2k-1}{k-1} + 2\binom{n+2k-2}{k-1}$$

and the lemma follows from (38). □

Using Lemma 10 and (27), for even $n \geq 4$, we find

$$2P_n(x) = P_{n-1}(x+1) + (x + \frac{n}{2} - 1)(x + \frac{n}{2} - 2) \cdots (x+1), \tag{39}$$

while, for odd $n \geq 3$,

$$P_n(x) = (2x+n)P_{n-1}(x+1) + (x + \frac{n-1}{2})(x + \frac{n-1}{2} - 1) \cdots (x+1).$$

Proposition 11. For odd $n \geq 3$, we have $P_n(k) \equiv P_n(0) \pmod{n}$.

Proof. From (36) we find that $\sum_{i=1}^k P_{n-1}(i) = (P_n(k) - P_n(0))/n$, and the proposition follows. □

9. On the Coefficients of $P_n(x)$

Using formulas (25) and (26), we give a recursion for the calculation of the coefficients of $P_n(x)$ with a fixed parity of n . Let

$$P_n(x) = a_0(n)x^m + a_1(n)x^{m-1} + \cdots + a_{m-1}(n)x + a_m(n),$$

where $m = \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$. We prove the following.

Theorem 12. For $n \geq 1$, we have

$$a_0(n) = \begin{cases} n, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{n}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even;} \end{cases} \tag{40}$$

$$a_1(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{24}(7n^3 - 12n^2 + 5n) & = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{24}n(n-1)(7n-5), & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ \frac{1}{48}n(n-2)(7n-4), & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \end{cases} \tag{41}$$

In general, for a fixed i , $a_i(n) = U_i(n)$, if n is odd, and $a_i(n) = V_i(n)$, if n is even, where U_i and V_i are polynomials in n of degree $2i + 1$.

Proof. **Case 1).** Let n be even. Then, using (26), for integer x and $m = \frac{n-2}{2}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (2x + n - 1)(a_0(n)x^m + a_1(n)x^{m-1} + \dots) = \\ & 2(x + n - 1)(x + n - 2)(a_0(n-2)x^{m-1} + a_1(n-2)x^{m-2} + \dots) + \\ & \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{n-2}{2}\right)! (4x + 3n - 4) \binom{x-1 + \frac{n-2}{2}}{\frac{n-2}{2}}. \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

Comparing the coefficient of x^{m+1} on both sides, we find

$$a_0(n) = a_0(n - 2) + 1, \quad n \geq 4, \quad a_0(4) = 2.$$

Thus $a_0(6) = 3, a_0(8) = 4, \dots, a_0(n) = n/2$.

Furthermore, comparing the coefficient of x^m on both sides of (42), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & 2a_1(n) + (n - 1)a_0(n) = 2a_1(n - 2) + 2(2n - 3)a_0(n - 2) + \\ & \text{Coe}f[x^m] \left(\frac{1}{2}(4x + 3n - 4)\left(x + \frac{n-4}{2}\right)\left(x + \frac{n-6}{2}\right) \cdots (x + 1)x\right). \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Coe}f[x^m] \left(\frac{1}{2}(4x + 3n - 4)\left(x + \frac{n-4}{2}\right)\left(x + \frac{n-6}{2}\right) \cdots (x + 1)x\right) = \\ & \frac{3n-4}{2} + 2\left(\frac{n-4}{2} + \frac{n-6}{2} + \dots + 1\right) = \\ & \frac{3n-4}{2} + \sum_{i=2}^m (n-2i) = \frac{n^2}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by (43),

$$a_1(n) - a_1(n - 2) = \frac{(2n - 3)(n - 2)}{2} - \frac{(n - 1)n}{4} + \frac{n^2}{8} = \frac{7n^2 - 26n + 24}{8}.$$

Hence

$$a_1(n) = \sum_{i=4,6,\dots,n} (a_1(i) - a_1(i-2)) = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{i=4,6,\dots,n} (7i^2 - 26i + 24) =$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=2}^{n/2} (7j^2 - 13j + 6) = \frac{1}{48}(7n^3 - 18n^2 + 8n).$$

Finally, comparing the coefficient of x^{m-i} on both sides of (42), we find

$$2a_{i+1}(n) + (n-1)a_i(n) = 2a_{i+1}(n-2) +$$

$$2(2n-3)a_i(n-2) + 2(n-1)(n-2)a_{i-1}(n-2) +$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \text{Coe}f[x^{m-i}]((4x+3n-4)(x+\frac{n-4}{2})(x+\frac{n-6}{2}) \cdots (x+1)(x)). \quad (44)$$

Note that, polynomial $(4x+3n-4)(x+\frac{n-4}{2})(x+\frac{n-6}{2}) \cdots (x+1)x$ has degree $m+1$. Therefore, in order to calculate $\text{Coe}f[x^{m-i}]$ in (44), we should choose, in all possible ways, in $m-i$ brackets (from $m+1$ ones) x 's, and for the other $i+1$ brackets we choose linear forms of n . Thus $\frac{1}{2}\text{Coe}f[x^{m-i}]$ in (44) is a polynomial $r_i(n)$ of degree $i+1$. Further we use induction over i with the formulas (40) and (41) as the inductive base. Write (44) in the form

$$2(a_{i+1}(n) - a_{i+1}(n-2)) =$$

$$2(2n-3)a_i(n-2) - (n-1)a_i(n) + 2(n-1)(n-2)a_{i-1}(n-2) + r_i(n). \quad (45)$$

By the inductive supposition, $a_{i-1}(n)$ and $a_i(n)$ are polynomials of degree $2i-1$ and $2i+1$ respectively. Thus $a_{i+1}(n) - a_{i+1}(n-2)$ is a polynomial of degree $2i+2$. This means that $a_{i+1}(n)$ is a polynomial of degree $2i+3$.

Case 2). Let n be odd. By (25), for integer x and $m = \frac{n-1}{2}$, we have

$$(2x+n-2)(a_0(n)x^m + a_1(n)x^{m-1} + \cdots) =$$

$$2(x+n-1)(x+n-2)(a_0(n-2)x^{m-1} + a_1(n-2)x^{m-2} + \cdots) +$$

$$\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)!(4x+3n-4) \binom{x+\frac{n-3}{2}}{\frac{n-1}{2}}. \quad (46)$$

Hence, comparing the coefficient of x^{m+1} on both sides, we find

$$a_0(n) = a_0(n-2) + 2, \quad n \geq 3, \quad a_0(1) = 1.$$

Thus $a_0(3) = 3, a_0(5) = 5, \dots, a_0(n) = n$.

Furthermore, comparing the coefficient of x^m on both sides of (46), using the same arguments as in 1), we have

$$a_1(n) = a_1(n - 2) + \frac{7n^2 - 22n + 19}{4}, \quad n \geq 3, \quad a_1(1) = 0.$$

Since $a_1(n) = \sum_{i=3,5,\dots,n} (a_1(i) - a_1(i - 2))$, we find

$$a_1(n) = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=3,5,\dots,n} (7i^2 - 22i + 19) = \frac{1}{24}(7n^3 - 12n^2 + 5n).$$

Finally, comparing the coefficient of x^{m-i} on both sides of (46), we find

$$\begin{aligned} 2(a_{i+1}(n) - a_{i+1}(n - 2)) = \\ 2(2n - 3)a_i(n - 2) - (n - 2)a_i(n) + \\ 2(n - 1)(n - 2)a_{i-1}(n - 2) + s_i(n), \end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

where

$$s_i(n) = \text{Coeff}[x^{m-i}]((4x + 3n - 4)(x + \frac{n-3}{2})(x + \frac{n-5}{2}) \cdots (x + 1)x)$$

and, as in 1), the statement is proved by induction over i . □

A few such polynomials are the following:

For odd n :

$$\begin{aligned} U_0(n) &= n, \\ U_1(n) &= \frac{1}{24}(n - 1)n(7n - 5), \\ U_2(n) &= \frac{1}{640}(n - 3)(n - 1)n(29n^2 - 44n + 7), \\ U_3(n) &= \frac{1}{322560}(n - 5)(n - 3)(n - 1)n(1581n^3 - 3775n^2 + 1587n + 223); \end{aligned}$$

For even n :

$$\begin{aligned} V_0(n) &= \frac{1}{2}n, \\ V_1(n) &= \frac{1}{48}(n - 2)n(7n - 4), \\ V_2(n) &= \frac{1}{3840}(n - 4)(n - 2)n(87n^2 - 98n + 16), \\ V_3(n) &= \frac{1}{645120}(n - 6)(n - 4)(n - 2)n(1581n^3 - 2686n^2 + 936n + 64). \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 13.

$$a_i(n) \equiv \begin{cases} r_i(n), & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ s_i(n), & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \pmod{2}$$

Proof. The proposition follows from (45), (47) and Theorem 2. □

Finally, note that, from (36) and (37) the following homogeneous recursions for the coefficients of $P_n(x)$ follow.

Theorem 14. For odd $n \geq 3$ and $i \geq 0$,

$$(m - i)a_i(n) = na_i(n - 1) + \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} (-1)^{i-j+1} \binom{m - j}{m - i - 1} a_j(n).$$

For even $n \geq 4$ and $i \geq 0$,

$$(n - 2i - 1)a_i(n) = \frac{n}{2}a_i(n - 1) + 2 \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} (-1)^{i-j+1} \left(m \binom{m - j}{m - i} - \binom{m - j}{m - i - 1} \right) a_j(n).$$

10. Arithmetic Proof of the Integrality $P_n(x)$ in Integer Points

From Theorem 2 we conclude that the polynomial, $P_n(x)$, takes integer values for integer $x = k$. Here we give an independent arithmetic proof of this fact using the explicit expression (3). It is well known (cf. [5], Section 8, Problem 87) that, if a polynomial $P(x)$ of degree m takes integer values for $x = 0, 1, \dots, m$, then it takes integer values for every integer x . Since, as we proved at the end of Section 6, $\deg P_n(k) = \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$, we suppose that $0 \leq k \leq \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$. Moreover, from the results of Section 3, $P_n(0)$ and $P_n(1)$ are integers. (In the case when $n + 1$ is an odd prime, $P_n(1) = (2^n - 1)(\frac{n}{2})!/(n + 1)$ is integer, since $2^n - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{n + 1}$, while in the case when $n + 1$ is an odd composite number, no divisor exceeds $\frac{n+1}{3}$, therefore, $(\frac{n}{2})! \equiv 0 \pmod{n + 1}$.) Thus we can suppose that

$$2 \leq k \leq \lfloor \frac{n - 1}{2} \rfloor. \tag{48}$$

Suppose that n is even (the case of odd n is considered quite analogously). Let p be a prime. Denote the maximal power of p dividing n by $[n]_p$. We say that, for integer l, h , the fraction $\frac{l}{h}$ is p -integer, if $[l]_p - [h]_p \geq 0$.

A) Firstly, we show that, for $n \geq 4$, $P_n(k)$ is 2-integer. Indeed, $2k + n - 1$ is odd, while $4k + 3n - 4$ is even. Therefore, by (26), using a trivial induction, we see that $P_n(k)$ is 2-integer.

Further we use the explicit formula (3) of Theorem 1.

B) Let p be an odd prime divisor of $\binom{n+2k-2}{k-1}$ which does not coincide with any factor of the product $(n+2k-1)(n+2k-2) \cdots (n+k)$. Thus p could divide one or several *composite* factors of this product. Therefore, the following condition holds

$$3 \leq p \leq \frac{n+2k-1}{3}. \tag{49}$$

Let us show that

$$a(n; k) = \frac{\binom{\frac{n}{2}+k-1}{k}}{\binom{n+2k-1}{k}} \left(\frac{n-2}{2}\right)! = 2^{-k} \frac{(n+2k-2)(n+2k-4) \cdots n}{(n+2k-1)(n+2k-2) \cdots (n+k)} \left(\frac{n-2}{2}\right)!$$

is p -integer and, consequently, $P_n(k)$ is p -integer.

Let $k \geq 3$ be even. Then, after a simplification, we have

$$2^k a(n; k) = \frac{(n+k-2)(n+k-4) \cdots n}{(n+2k-1)(n+2k-3) \cdots (n+k+1)} \left(\frac{n-2}{2}\right)!,$$

or

$$2^{\frac{k}{2}} a(n; k) = \frac{\left(\frac{n+k-2}{2}\right)!}{(n+2k-1)(n+2k-3) \cdots (n+k+1)} \tag{50}$$

We distinguish several cases.

Case a). For $t \geq 2$, let p^t divide at least one factor of the denominator. Then $p \leq (n+2k-1)^{\frac{1}{t}}$. Let us show that $p \leq \frac{n+k-2}{2t}$. We should show that $n+2k-1 \leq \left(\frac{n+k-2}{2t}\right)^t$, or, since, by (48), $k \leq \frac{n-2}{2}$, it is sufficient to show that $\frac{3}{2}(n+k-2) \leq \left(\frac{n+k-2}{2t}\right)^t$, or $(2t)^{\frac{t}{t-1}} \leq \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{t-1}}(n+k-2)$. Since $\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{t-1}} \geq \frac{2}{3}$, it is sufficient to prove that $(2t)^{\frac{t}{t-1}} \leq \frac{2}{3}(n+k-2)$. Note that $e^t < p^t \leq n+2k-2$, $t \leq \ln(n+2k-2)$. Therefore we find $(2t)^{\frac{t}{t-1}} \leq (2 \ln(n+2k-2))^2$. Furthermore, note that, if $n \geq 152$, then $\ln^2 n < \frac{n}{6}$. Thus $(2t)^{\frac{t}{t-1}} \leq \frac{2}{3}(n+k-2)$. It is left to add that up to $n = 161$ we verified that the polynomials $P_n(k)$ have integer coefficients and, consequently, is integer-valued.

Case b). Let p divide only one factor of the denominator. Then, in view of (48) and (49), $p \leq \frac{n+2k-1}{3} \leq \frac{n+k-2}{2}$ and, by (50), $a(n; k)$ is p -integer.

Case c). Let p divide exactly l factors of the denominator. Then

$$p \leq \frac{(n+2k-1) - (n+k+1)}{l} = \frac{k-2}{l},$$

and, since, by (48), $n \geq 2k + 2$, we conclude that $\frac{n+k-2}{2} \geq \frac{3k}{2} \geq k - 2 \geq lp$. Hence, by (50), $a(n; k)$ is p -integer.

It is left to notice that the case of odd k is considered quite analogously.

C) Suppose that, as in B), $k \geq 2$ is even. Let p be an odd prime divisor of $\binom{n+2k-1}{k}$ which coincides with some factor of the product $(n+2k-1)(n+2k-3) \cdots (n+k+1)$. In this case the fraction (50) is not integer. Thus in order to prove that $P_n(k)$ is p -integer, we should prove that $T_n(k)$ (18) is p -integer. By the condition, p has form

$$p = n + 2k - 1 - 2r, \quad 0 \leq r \leq \frac{k-2}{2}. \tag{51}$$

According to (18) and (51), we should prove that

$$\sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 2^j \binom{n+2k-j-2}{k-1} = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 2^j \binom{p+2r-1-j}{k-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \tag{52}$$

or

$$A(n, r, k) :=$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^{n-1} 2^j (j - (2r - 1))(j + 1 - (2r - 1)) \cdots (j + k - 2 - (2r - 1)) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

Note that, since $n - 2r = p - 2k + 1$, we have

$$\sum_{j=0}^{n-1} x^{j+k-2-(2r-1)} = (x^{n+k-2r-1} - x^{k-2r-1})(x-1)^{-1} = (x^{p-k} - x^{k-2r-1})(x-1)^{-1}.$$

Therefore,

$$A(n, r, k) = 2^{2r} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} (x^{j+k-2-(2r-1)})^{(k-1)} \Big|_{x=2} = 2^{2r} ((x^{p-k} - x^{k-2r-1})(x-1)^{-1})^{(k-1)} \Big|_{x=2}.$$

Thus we should prove that

$$((x^{p-k} - x^{k-2r-1})(x-1)^{-1})^{(k-1)} \Big|_{x=2} \equiv 0 \pmod{p},$$

or, using the Leibnitz formula,

$$\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j-1} \binom{k-1}{j} (k-j-1)! (p-k)(p-k-1) \cdots (p-k-j+1) 2^{p-k-j} \equiv$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j-1} \binom{k-1}{j} (k-j-1)! (k-2r-1)(k-2r-2) \cdots (k-2r-j) 2^{k-2r-j-1} \pmod{p}.$$

Since $2^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, we should prove the identity

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j-1} \binom{k-1}{k-j-1} (k-j-1)! (p-k)(p-k-1) \cdots (p-k-j+1) \Big|_{p=0} 2^{-k-j+1} = \\ & \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-j-1} \binom{k-1}{k-j-1} (k-j-1)! (k-2r-1)(k-2r-2) \cdots (k-2r-j) 2^{k-2r-j-1}, \end{aligned}$$

or, after simple transformations, the identity

$$\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \binom{k+j-1}{j} 2^{-j} = 2^{2k-2r-2} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^j \binom{k-2r-1}{j} 2^{-j}. \tag{53}$$

It is known ([7], Ch.1, problem 7), that

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \binom{2n-i}{n} 2^{i-n} = 2^n.$$

Putting $n - i = j$, we have

$$\sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n+j}{n} 2^{-j} = \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n+j}{j} 2^{-j} = 2^n.$$

Therefore, the left hand side of (53) is 2^{k-1} and it is left to prove that

$$\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^j \binom{k-2r-1}{j} 2^{k-j} = 2^{2r+1}.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} (-1)^j \binom{k-2r-1}{j} 2^{k-j} = \sum_{j=0}^{k-2r-1} (-1)^j \binom{k-2r-1}{j} 2^{k-j} = \\ & 2^{2r+1} \sum_{j=0}^{k-2r-1} (-1)^j \binom{k-2r-1}{j} 2^{k-2r-1-j} = 2^{2r+1} (2-1)^{k-2r-1} = 2^{2r+1} \end{aligned}$$

and we are done. The case of odd $k \geq 3$ is considered quite analogously. So, formulas (50) and (51) take the form

$$\begin{aligned} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} a(n; k) &= \frac{\left(\frac{n+k-1}{2}\right)!}{(n+2k-1)(n+2k-3) \cdots (n+k)}, \\ p &= n + 2k - 2r - 1, \quad 0 \leq r \leq \frac{k-1}{2}, \end{aligned}$$

and, for odd k , the proof reduces to the same congruence (52).

11. Representation of $P_n(x)$ in Basis $\{\binom{x}{i}\}$

The structure of the explicit formula (3) allows us to conjecture that the coefficients of $P_n(x)$ in basis $\{\binom{x}{i}\}$ have simpler properties. A process of expansion of a polynomial $P(x)$ in the binomial basis is indicated in [5] in a solution of Problem 85: “Functions $1, x, x^2, \dots, x^n$ one can consecutively express in the form of linear combinations with the constant coefficients of $1, \frac{x}{1}, \frac{x(x-1)}{2}, \dots, \frac{x(x-1)\dots(x-n+1)}{n!}$.” Therefore,

$$P(x) = b_0 \binom{x}{m} + b_1 \binom{x}{m-1} + \dots + b_{m-1} \binom{x}{1} + b_m,$$

where $b_0, b_1, \dots, b_m$ are defined from the equations

$$\begin{aligned} P(0) &= b_m, \\ P(1) &= b_m + \binom{1}{1} b_{m-1}, \\ P(2) &= b_m + \binom{2}{1} b_{m-1} + \binom{2}{2} b_{m-2}, \\ &\vdots \\ P(m) &= b_m + \binom{m}{1} b_{m-1} + \dots + \binom{m}{m} b_0. \end{aligned}$$

This process can be simplified in the following way. In the identity

$$\begin{aligned} n^x &= (1 + (n - 1))^x = \\ &= 1 + (n - 1) \binom{x}{1} + (n - 1)^2 \binom{x}{2} + \dots + (n - 1)^x \binom{x}{x} = \\ &= n^0 + (n - n^0) \binom{x}{1} + (n - n^0)^2 \binom{x}{2} + \dots + (n - n^0)^x \binom{x}{x} \end{aligned}$$

we can evidently replace powers $n^j, j = 0, \dots, x$, by the arbitrary numbers $a_j, j = 0, \dots, x$. Thus we have a general identity

$$\begin{aligned} a_x &= a_0 + (a_1 - a_0) \binom{x}{1} + (a_2 - 2a_1 + a_0) \binom{x}{2} + (a_3 - 3a_2 + 3a_1 - a_0) \binom{x}{3} + \dots + \\ &= (a_x - \binom{x}{1} a_{x-1} + \binom{x}{2} a_{x-2} - \dots + (-1)^x \binom{x}{x} a_0) \binom{x}{x}. \end{aligned}$$

Essentially, we quickly obtained a special case of the so-called “Newton’s forward difference formula” (cf. [10]). Here, put $a_j = P(j), j = 0, \dots, m$, and, firstly,

consider values $0 \leq x \leq m$. Since $\binom{x}{l} = 0$ for $l > m$, we obtain the required representation under the condition $0 \leq x \leq m$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(x) &= P(0) + (P(1) - P(0))\binom{x}{1} + \\
 &(P(2) - 2P(1) + P(0))\binom{x}{2} + \cdots + (P(m) - \binom{m}{1}P(m-1) + \\
 &\binom{m}{2}P(m-2) - \cdots + (-1)^m \binom{m}{m}P(0))\binom{x}{m}. \tag{54}
 \end{aligned}$$

It is left to note that, since a polynomial of degree m is fully defined by its values in $m + 1$ points $0, 1, \dots, m$, then (54) is the required representation for all x .

So, for the polynomials $\{P_n(x)\}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 &= 1, \\
 P_2 &= 1, \\
 P_3 &= 3\binom{x}{1} + 4, \\
 P_4 &= 2\binom{x}{1} + 4, \\
 P_5 &= 10\binom{x}{2} + 30\binom{x}{1} + 32, \\
 P_6 &= 6\binom{x}{2} + 22\binom{x}{1} + 32, \\
 P_7 &= 42\binom{x}{3} + 196\binom{x}{2} + 378\binom{x}{1} + 384, \\
 P_8 &= 24\binom{x}{3} + 128\binom{x}{2} + 296\binom{x}{1} + 384, \\
 P_9 &= 216\binom{x}{4} + 1368\binom{x}{3} + 3816\binom{x}{2} + 6120\binom{x}{1} + 6144, \\
 P_{10} &= 120\binom{x}{4} + 840\binom{x}{3} + 2664\binom{x}{2} + 5016\binom{x}{1} + 6144, \\
 P_{11} &= 1320\binom{x}{5} + 10560\binom{x}{4} + 38544\binom{x}{3} + 84480\binom{x}{2} + 122760\binom{x}{1} + 122880, \\
 P_{12} &= 760\binom{x}{5} + 6240\binom{x}{4} + 25152\binom{x}{3} + 62112\binom{x}{2} + 103920\binom{x}{1} + 122880.
 \end{aligned}$$

12. On Coefficients of $P_n(x)$ in Basis $\{\binom{x}{i}\}$

Let

$$P_n(x) = b_0(n)\binom{x}{m} + b_1(n)\binom{x}{m-1} + \dots + b_{m-1}(n)\binom{x}{1} + b_m(n),$$

where $m = \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$.

Since, for integer k , we have the explicit formula for $P_n(k)$, (3), then, according to (54), we have the following explicit formula for $b_i(n)$, $i = 0, \dots, m$:

$$b_i(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{m-i} (-1)^{m-i-k} \binom{m-i}{k} P_n(k). \tag{55}$$

Let

$$P_n(x) = \sum_{j=0}^m a_j(n)x^{m-j}.$$

Then

$$b_i(n) = \sum_{j=0}^m a_j(n) \sum_{k=0}^{m-i} (-1)^{m-i-k} k^{m-j} \binom{m-i}{k}. \tag{56}$$

Since the l -th difference of $f(x)$ is (cf. [1], formula 25.1.1)

$$\Delta^l f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^l (-1)^{l-k} \binom{l}{k} f(x+k),$$

one can write (56) in the form

$$b_i(n) = \sum_{j=0}^m a_j(n) \Delta^{m-i} x^{m-j} \Big|_{x=0}.$$

Here the summands corresponding to $j > i$, evidently, equal 0. Therefore, we have

$$b_i(n) = \sum_{j=0}^i a_j(n) \Delta^{m-i} x^{m-j} \Big|_{x=0}. \tag{57}$$

Theorem 15. *For $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$b_0(n) = \begin{cases} n\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)!, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ \left(\frac{n}{2}\right)!, & \text{if } n \text{ is even;} \end{cases} \tag{58}$$

$$b_1(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{6}n(5n-7)\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)!, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd,} \\ \frac{1}{6}(5n-8)\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)!, & \text{if } n \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \tag{59}$$

In general, for a fixed i , $b_i(n) = (m-i)!Y_i(n)$, if n is odd, and $b_i(n) = (m-i)!Z_i(n)$, if n is even, where Y_i and Z_i are polynomials in n of degree $2i + 1$.

Proof. Note that the Stirling number of the second kind $S(n, m)$ is connected with the m -th difference of $\Delta^m x^n |_{x=0}$ in the following way (see [1], formulas 24.1.4):

$$S(n, m)m! = \sum_{k=0}^m (-1)^{m-k} \binom{m}{k} k^n = \Delta^m x^n |_{x=0} . \tag{60}$$

In particular, since $S(m, m) = 1$, $S(m + 1, m) = \binom{m+1}{2}$, we have

$$\Delta^m x^m |_{x=0} = m!$$

and

$$\Delta^m x^{m+1} |_{x=0} = \frac{m}{2}(m + 1)! .$$

Therefore, by (57),

$$b_0(n) = m!a_0(n),$$

$$b_1(n) = \frac{m-1}{2}m!a_0(n) + (m-1)!a_1(n),$$

and, by (40) and (41) (where $m = \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$), we find formulas (58) and (59).

Further, we need the following lemma.

Lemma 16. $S(n + k, n)$ is a polynomial in n of degree $2k$.

Proof. For $k \geq 1$, let

$$Q_k(n) = S(n + k, n).$$

Note that, since $S(n, n) = 1$, we have $Q_0(n) = 1$. Further, since $S(n, 0) = \delta_{n,0}$, for $k \geq 1$, $Q_k(0) = 0$. From the main recursion for $S(n, m)$ which is $S(n, m) = mS(n - 1, m) + S(n - 1, m - 1)$, we have

$$Q_k(n) - Q_k(n - 1) = nQ_{k-1}(n).$$

Also, in view of $Q_k(0) = 0$, we find the recursion

$$Q_0(n) = 1, \quad Q_k(n) = \sum_{i=1}^n iQ_{k-1}(i). \tag{61}$$

Using a simple induction, from (61) we obtain the lemma. □

Remark 17. The first few polynomials $\{Q_k(n)\}$ are:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_0 &= 1, \\ Q_1 &= \frac{1}{2}n(n+1), \\ Q_2 &= \frac{1}{24}n(n+1)(n+2)(3n+1), \\ Q_3 &= \frac{1}{48}n^2(n+1)^2(n+2)(n+3), \\ Q_4 &= \frac{1}{5760}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(15n^3+30n^2+5n-2). \end{aligned}$$

It can be proven that the sequence of denominators coincides with A053657 [8], such that the denominator of $Q_k(n)$ is $\prod p^{\sum_{j \geq 0} \lfloor \frac{k}{(p-1)p^j} \rfloor}$, where the product is over all primes.

Note that from (57) and (60) we find

$$b_i(n) = (m-i)! \sum_{j=0}^i a_j(n)S(m-j, m-i), \quad m = \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor.$$

Since, by Lemma 10, $S(m-j, m-i)$ is a polynomial in n of degree $2((m-j) - (m-i)) = 2(i-j)$, while, by Theorem 12, $a_j(n)$ is a polynomial of degree $2j+1$, it follows that $a_j(n)S(m-j, m-i)$ is a polynomial of degree $2i+1$. Thus $\sum_{j=0}^i a_j(n)S(m-j, m-i)$ is a polynomial of degree $2i+1$. This completes the proof. $\square$

The first polynomials $Y_i(n)$, $Z_i(n)$ are

$$\begin{aligned} Y_0 &= n, \\ Y_1 &= \frac{1}{12}(n-1)n(5n-7), \\ Y_2 &= \frac{1}{480}(n-3)(n-1)n(43n^2-168n+149), \\ Y_3 &= \frac{1}{13440}(n-5)(n-3)(n-1)n(177n^3-1319n^2+3063n-2161); \\ Z_0 &= \frac{n}{2}, \\ Z_1 &= \frac{1}{24}(n-2)n(5n-8), \\ Z_2 &= \frac{1}{960}(n-4)(n-2)n(43n^2-182n+184), \\ Z_3 &= \frac{1}{26880}(n-6)(n-4)(n-2)n(3n-8)(59n^2-306n+352). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we prove the following attractive result.

Theorem 18. 1) For odd n , $b_j(n)/n, j = 0, \dots, m - 1$, are integer. Moreover, for $n \geq 3$,

$$b_i(n) = n(b_i(n - 1) + b_{i-1}(n - 1)), \quad i = 1, \dots, m - 1.$$

2) For even $n \geq 4$,

$$2b_i(n) = b_i(n - 1) + b_{i-1}(n - 1) + m! \binom{m}{i}, \quad i = 1, \dots, m - 1. \quad (62)$$

Proof. 1) According to (55), we should prove that for odd $n \geq 3$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^{m-i} (-1)^{m-i-k} \binom{m-i}{k} P_n(k) = \\ & n \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-i} (-1)^{m-i-k} \binom{m-i}{k} P_{n-1}(k) + \right. \\ & \left. \sum_{k=0}^{m-i-1} (-1)^{m-i-k-1} \binom{m-i-1}{k} P_{n-1}(k) \right), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1, \end{aligned}$$

or, putting $m - i = t$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^t (-1)^k \binom{t}{k} P_n(k) &= n \left(\sum_{k=0}^t (-1)^k \binom{t}{k} P_{n-1}(k) - \right. \\ & \left. \sum_{k=0}^t (-1)^k \binom{t-1}{k} P_{n-1}(k) \right), \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1, \end{aligned}$$

or, finally, for $t = 1, \dots, \frac{n-3}{2}$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^t (-1)^{k-1} \left(\binom{t}{k} P_n(k) - \binom{t-1}{k-1} n P_{n-1}(k) \right) = P_n(0). \quad (63)$$

To prove (63), note that, by (36), $nP_{n-1}(k) = P_n(k) - P_n(k - 1)$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \binom{t}{k} P_n(k) - \binom{t-1}{k-1} n P_{n-1}(k) = \\ & P_n(k) \left(\binom{t}{k} - \binom{t-1}{k-1} \right) + \binom{t-1}{k-1} P_n(k-1) = \\ & \binom{t-1}{k} P_n(k) + \binom{t-1}{k-1} P_n(k-1). \end{aligned}$$

Thus the summands of (63) are

$$(-1)^{k-1} \left(\binom{t}{k} P_n(k) - \binom{t-1}{k-1} n P_{n-1}(k) \right) =$$

$$(-1)^{k-1} \binom{t-1}{k} P_n(k) - (-1)^{k-2} \binom{t-1}{k-1} P_n(k-1),$$

and the summing gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^t (-1)^{k-1} \left(\binom{t}{k} P_n(k) - \binom{t-1}{k-1} n P_{n-1}(k) \right) = \\ & (-1)^{k-1} \binom{t-1}{k} P_n(k) \Big|_{k=t} - (-1)^{k-2} \binom{t-1}{k-1} P_n(k-1) \Big|_{k=1} = P_n(0). \end{aligned}$$

2) Analogously, the proof of (62) reduces to the proof of the following equality for $t = 1, 2, \dots, m - 1$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{t+1} (-1)^k \left(2 \binom{t}{k} P_n(k) + \binom{t}{k-1} P_{n-1}(k) \right) = (-1)^t m! \binom{m}{t}. \tag{64}$$

Note that, by (39),

$$\begin{aligned} & (-1)^k \left(2 \binom{t}{k} P_n(k) + \binom{t}{k-1} P_{n-1}(k) \right) = \\ & (-1)^k \binom{t}{k} P_{n-1}(k+1) - \\ & (-1)^{k-1} \binom{t}{k-1} P_{n-1}(k) + (-1)^k \binom{t}{k} \binom{k+m}{m} m! \end{aligned} \tag{65}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^{t+1} \left((-1)^k \binom{t}{k} P_{n-1}(k+1) - (-1)^{k-1} \binom{t}{k-1} P_{n-1}(k) \right) = \\ & (-1)^k \binom{t}{k} P_{n-1}(k) \Big|_{k=t+1} - (-1)^{k-1} \binom{t}{k-1} P_{n-1}(k) \Big|_{k=0} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

by (64) and (65), the proof reduces to the known combinatorial identity

$$\sum_{k=0}^t (-1)^k \binom{t}{k} \binom{k+m}{m} = (-1)^t \binom{m}{t}, \quad t = 1, \dots, m - 1$$

(see [7], Ch.1, formula (8) with $p = 0$ up to the notations). □

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